

TCAD investigation of Compensated LGAD Sensors for extreme fluence

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ABSTRACT

A new gain layer design, whose effective doping profile results from the difference between two overlapping implants of opposite dopant species (e.g. boron and phosphorus), is conceived to extend the operational life of Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs) to fluences significantly above the present limit of $2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ $1 \text{ MeV } n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$. Both acceptor and donor atoms will experience doping removal due to irradiation, but their difference will remain fairly constant.

The implementation of this ambitious goal necessitates a meticulous process of optimizing the two implants that constitute the gain layer of the Compensated LGADs. To this end, the Synopsys[®] Sentaurus TCAD toolkit, with the most up-to-date release of the Perugia radiation damage model, was employed, enabling a comprehensive investigation of these new sensors. This level of scrutiny is crucial for understanding the behaviour of the first Compensated LGAD production (2022 by FBK) and designing the subsequent batches of Compensated LGADs.

1. Introduction

In future hadron collider experiments, it is crucial to have 4D tracking to accurately reconstruct the events of interest in the thousand collisions per bunch crossing. Timing-optimized Low Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs), also known as Ultra-Fast Silicon Detectors (UFSDs), have shown the ability to achieve the required timing resolutions of $\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ ps})$ [1]. However, they cannot withstand the expected harsh radiation environments, with fluences $\geq 10^{17}$ $1 \text{ MeV } n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$.

The gain layer in standard LGADs is made by a single acceptor dopant implant, which is almost completely deactivated at about $2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ $1 \text{ MeV } n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ due to the acceptor removal mechanism [2]. To achieve precision timing at higher fluences, an exciting and innovative idea is to make the gain layer as the superposition of two implants of opposite dopant species (e.g. boron and phosphorus), resulting in a difference, i.e. an effective doping equal to that typically found in standard LGADs. Both implants will undergo dopant removal due to irradiation; however, if properly engineered, their difference will

remain fairly constant (Fig. 1), thus guaranteeing full functionality of the Compensated LGADs [3] at the required fluences.

2. TCAD simulations & experimental measurements

Several questions still need to be addressed to manufacture fully functional Compensated LGADs. For example, how fast does the donor doping deactivate compared to the acceptor? Do acceptor and donor removal behave similarly when present simultaneously or individually? Additionally, does donor doping change the carbon effect (i.e., slow acceptor removal)? Answers can be found by comparing TCAD simulations with experimental measurements of Compensated LGADs from their first batch [4], i.e. the proof-of-concept released by FBK at the end of 2022. In the latter, three different combinations of acceptor and donor doses — 2–1, 3–2, and 5–4 — were investigated. The first number indicates how many FBK standard doses¹ are used for the boron implant and the second number those for the phosphorus implant.

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¹ FBK standard dose = Dose used for the gain layer in standard LGADs.

Fig. 1. Evolution of the two gain layer designs (the standard one on the left column and the compensated one on the right column) with irradiation (unirradiated devices on the top row and irradiated ones on the bottom row). The boron gain layer in standard LGADs becomes completely deactivated above around $2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ 1 MeV n_{eq}/cm^2 due to acceptor removal. Meanwhile, in Compensated LGADs, the effective gain layer (the difference between the boron and phosphorus implants) is almost unchanged by irradiation. Although the individual implants experience acceptor and donor removal, their difference remains practically constant. As a result, it is possible to extend 4D tracking to significantly higher fluences than the current limit of standard LGADs.

However, regardless of the investigated combination, their difference is always equal to one FBK standard dose and thus, the effective compensated gain layer is the same as the standard one. Lastly, carbon was co-implanted in one wafer of the 3–2 combination to explore its impact on mitigating boron deactivation by irradiation in the presence of phosphorus atoms.

The comparison process began with a wafer of the 3–2 combination. Initially, the thickness and doping of the substrate were adjusted by comparing C-V simulations and measurements of p-i-n structures. Next, the two profiles of the compensated gain layer extracted from SIMSs were added, and the agreement with the pre-irradiation measurements was reassessed. Finally, post-irradiation² comparisons were conducted. During this analysis, the most recent release of the Perugia radiation damage model [5] was used in the TCAD environment. This model parameterizes acceptor and donor removal as follows:

$$N_{A,D}(\phi) = N_{A,D}(0) \cdot e^{-c_{A,D} \phi}$$

where $c_{A,D}$ is the acceptor (donor) removal coefficient depending on the initial acceptor (donor) concentration $N_{A,D}(0)$, and ϕ is the irradiation fluence in 1 MeV n_{eq}/cm^2 .

The c_A values for the acceptor doping concentrations employed in the Compensated LGADs are known from the analysis conducted on standard LGADs [2]. In contrast, different values of c_D were tried until a simulations-measurements agreement was reached in terms of C-V characteristics at different fluences. The results shown in Fig. 2 are obtained with $c_D = 6.50 \cdot 10^{-16}$ cm^2 and $c_A = 2.50 \cdot 10^{-16}$ cm^2 .

Using the previously extracted c_D , a good simulation-measurement agreement was also found for the wafer with carbon co-implantation. In this case, the c_A is $8.26 \cdot 10^{-17}$ cm^2 , i.e., one-third of the previous one, due to the presence of carbon, which slows down acceptor removal

Fig. 2. Pre- and post-irradiation C-V measurements and simulations. Each band is the plane area covered by the family of curves obtained by measuring different samples of the same wafer under the same conditions. Simulations at the various fluences well reproduce the depletion of the gain layer, i.e., the region before the knee, and the geometric capacitance.

compared to that in sensors without carbon to the same extent observed in standard LGADs [2].

3. Conclusion

Compensated LGADs represent the way to teleport planar sensors into future hadron collider experiments. Therefore, fully understanding and optimizing their operation is of the utmost importance. In this respect, comparing TCAD simulations and experimental measurements is an excellent strategy.

² Sensor irradiation was done at the JSI TRIGA Mark II neutron reactor in the fluence range $[4 \cdot 10^{14}, 5 \cdot 10^{15}]$ 1 MeV n_{eq}/cm^2 .

The initial comparison with the wafer data belonging to the 3–2 combination allowed us to estimate the donor removal rate, which was significantly faster than the acceptor removal rate. The subsequent comparison with the carbon co-implanted wafer data further confirmed this finding. The latter comparison also revealed that the presence of phosphorus does not seem to diminish the beneficial effect of carbon co-implantation compared to that observed in standard LGADs.

Upcoming simulation-measurement comparisons for wafers with combinations of acceptor and donor doses different from 3–2 will allow the c_D estimation for other $N_D(0)$. Upon completion, these data will represent valuable information for the process and design optimization of the next Compensated LGAD batches.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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